

Rice-based cropping systems

Economics of rainfed upland rice-based cropping systems in the northwestern Himalayas

Ved Prakash, V. S. Chauhan, and J. P. Tandon, Vivekananda Laboratory for Hill Agriculture, Almora, Uttar Pradesh, India

About 70% of 150,000-ha rice area in the Kumaon and Garhwal hills of Uttar Pradesh is in dryland rice. The most popular dryland 2-year rotation is rice (March-September) - wheat (October-May) - finger millet *Eleusine coracana* L. (June-October) - fallow (November-March). In this sequence, a 150% cropping intensity is obtained. Cropping intensity potential can be increased to 200% by direct seeding early-maturing rice varieties in June.

A 4-year fixed-plot field study at Vivekananda Parvatiya Krishi Anusandhan Shala (VPKAS) Experimental Farm, Hawalbagh (Almora), explored ways of increasing cropping system intensity. The local rotation was compared with five improved crop sequences, four of which used early-maturing experimental rice varieties.

Number of tillers, nitrogen concentration, and grain yield of kharif rice crops as influenced by dubari crops and nitrogen level

A. A. Jakhro and G. Faroque, Sind Agriculture University, Tando Jam, Sind, Pakistan

Rice is the major kharif crop in Sind Province, Pakistan. Several rabi season dubari crops are cultivated after rice. Crop patterns are rice - gram, rice - lucerne, rice - fallow, and rice - wheat.

A study was conducted to determine the effects of dubari crops on number of tillers, percent nitrogen concentration, grain yield, and nitrogen response of the kharif crop. In the first-year study, gram - rice, lucerne - rice, fallow - rice, and wheat - rice were examined in a com-

Grain yield, costs, and returns 1977-78 to 1980-81 for dryland cropping systems in Uttar Pradesh, India.^a

Cropping pattern	Rainy season yield (t/ha)	Winter yield (t/ha)	Total variable cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$+/ha)	Benefit-cost ratio
Rice - wheat	2.1	2.7	467	333	1.7
Rice - lentil	1.7	1.8	423	464	2.1
Rice - chickpea	1.9	2.2	457	711	2.6
Rice - pea	1.9	1.5	439	386	1.9
Spring rice - rapeseed	2.4	0.8	435	210	1.5
Spring rice - wheat	1.5	2.8	344	202	1.6
Finger millet - fallow	2.7				

^aCultivars used were VL206 (spring rice), experimental strains (June rice), VL421 (wheat), T36 (lentil), VL86 (chickpea), VL1 (pea), T9 (rapeseed), and VL101 (finger millet).

Average grain yield of June-seeded experimental varieties equaled that of spring-seeded rice. June seeding made 2 annual rice crops possible. Rapeseed (*Brassica campestris* L. var. *toria*), included in the spring sequence, produced a reasonably good yield (0.8 t/ha).

Highest average annual net return and benefit-cost ratios were recorded using a June-seeded rice - chickpea rotation followed by rice - lentil, rice - field pea, and rice - wheat sequences (see table). Results show that changing from tradi-

tional dryland rice rotations to more intensive cropping sequences using early-maturing varieties suitable for June seeding is profitable. Planting legumes in rabi season helps economize fertilizer use.

Improved cropping sequences provide a 2-week gap between harvest and seeding. Socioeconomic surveys indicate there is substantial underutilized human and bullock power in the hill villages to provide additional power requirements needed for more intensive crop rotations.

plete block design with four replications. Plot size was 5 m × 10 m. No plot received nitrogen but all received 30 kg P₂O₅/ha. IR8 rice seedlings were transplanted.

In the second-year study 0, 30, 60, 90, 120, and 150 kg N/ha were tested in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Half of the nitrogen and 30 kg P₂O₅/ha were broadcast and incorporated into the soil. Remaining nitrogen was topdressed 30 days after transplanting (DT).

Number of tillers and percent nitrogen concentration at 30 DT, and grain yield (t/ha) of the rice crop increased progressively and significantly after gram and lucerne (see table). However, the rice crops did not differ significantly in those characteristics.

Effect of dubari crops on number of tillers and nitrogen concentration at 30 days after transplanting, and on grain yield of kharif rice;^a Sind, Pakistan.

Crop pattern	Tillers (no./hill)	N concentration (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Gram - rice	55 a	2.5 a	3.6 a
Lucerne - rice	52 ab	2.5 ab	3.5 ab
Fallow - rice	45 c	2.3 c	2.5 c
Wheat - rice	35 d	1.8 d	1.9 d

^aMeans followed by common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Yield after gram and lucerne increased with nitrogen levels up to 90 kg/ha, but decreased beyond that level (see figure). After wheat, yield increased with nitrogen levels up to 120 kg/ha, then declined. Maximum yields of rice

grown after gram, lucerne, and wheat did not differ but a significant difference in nitrogen requirement was observed. However, kharif rice crop required 30 kg N/ha less when grown after gram and lucerne than after wheat.

Results suggest that biological nitrogen fixation by dubari crops after kharif rice benefits growth and grain yield of the next rice crop. ♪

Effect of nitrogen fertilizer on grain yield of kharif rice grown after dubari crops.

Announcements

Activities of the IRRI Japan Library Office

Kazuico Morooka and Yuko Sasajima, IRRI Japan Office, c/o National Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Yatabe, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305 Japan

Japanese scientists contributed about one-fourth of the world literature on rice that was cataloged in the 1979 International Bibliography of Rice Research (IBRR), published by the IRRI Library (see figure). About 80% of these materials are in Japanese, which reduces their impact on international agriculture. In anticipation of this shortcoming the IRRI Tokyo Office (now the Japan Office) at the National Institute of Agricultural Sciences was concurrently established with IRRI.

The Japan Office screens, collects, indexes, and translates published and

unpublished Japanese materials about rice research. Translating complete books on rice in cooperation with Japanese authors and researchers and writing English annotations of other works are an important function of the office.

More than 67,942 Japanese references were included in the IBRR between 1951 and 1979. All publications cited in the IBRR are available at the IRRI library and copies of IBRR have been distributed to the libraries of major universities and institutes associated with rice research throughout the world.

Since 1961 the Japan Office has translated 900 books and articles from Japanese to English. Translations are available at the IRRI library, the translation center of the John Crerar Library in Chicago, Illinois, USA, and the Japan Office. Lists of translations are in IBRR supplements published since 1964. ♪

Ratio of the number of publications written by Japanese scientists to the world rice literature.

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- An adventure in applied science: a history of the International Rice Research Institute*
- A methodology for on-farm cropping systems research*
- Fundamentals of rice crop science*
- Landless workers and rice farmers: peasant subclasses under agrarian reform in two Philippine villages*

- Major weeds of rice in South and Southeast Asia*
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